

**AFRICAN
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**Journal
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De la
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PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT, POST CONSOLIDATION OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES

BY

Prof. ADEYEMO K ADEREMI

INTRODUCTION

Product development is a process of creating new product to serve the need and wants of customers who are already buying a company's products, or services. It involves developing new products, modifying the existing ones, and dropping the old ones.

Developing a new product also involves determining the appearance and identification of the product, setting prices, discounts, terms of sale, allowances and integrating a product line.

The relevance of bank in the economy of any nation cannot be overemphasized. They are the cornerstones of the economy of any country. The economies of all market-oriented nations depend on the efficient operation of complex and delicately balanced systems of money and credit. Banks are indispensable elements in these systems. They provide the bulk of the money supply as well as the primary means of facilitating the flow of credit. Consequently, it is submitted that the economic well being of a nation is a function of advancement and development of her banking industry

The financial deregulation in Nigeria that started in 1987 and the associated financial innovations have generated an unprecedented degree of competition in the banking industry. The deregulation initially pivoted powerful incentive for the expansion of both size and number of banking and non-banking institutions. The consequent phenomenal increase in the number of banking and non-banking institutions providing financial services led to increased competition amongst various banking institutions, and between banks and non-banking financial intermediaries.

All these factors- deregulation, competition, innovation, economic recession, political instability, escalating inflation, and frequent reversal

of monetary policies have combined to create a challenging and precarious financial environment for banks.

Consequence of the new financial environment have been the rapidly declining profitability of the traditional banking activities. The continuing deterioration in the financial health of the banks and increasing incidence of bank failure since deregulation have raised question about the nature and state of Nigeria Banking sector.

As business is about creating and retaining customers, the life of any business is directly proportional to its ability to continue to deliver sustainable superior competitive advantage (Value) over rivals. A good product development policy is vital in order to win customers confidence back in the industry.

What is Product Development?

- ✓ A product is anything that can be offered to market to satisfy a want or need. Products that are marketed include physical goods, services, experiences, events, persons, places, organizations, information, and ideas (Kotler and Keller, 2006)
- ✓ A product is a need satisfying offers of a firm (W.D Perrault & R.J) McCarty, 2002).
- ✓ A product is something that has the capacity to give satisfaction (Onah & Thomas, 2004)
- ✓ Development is a process of creating new things, making things to happen; Product evolution, which includes, exploration, screening, business analysis, development, testing and commercialization in order to produce a product.

Types of New Products That Can Be Developed

The development route can take two forms. The company can develop new products in its own laboratories, or it can contract with independent researchers of new products as stated below.

1. New-to-the-world product - New products that create an entirely new market.
2. New product lines - New products that allow a company to enter established markets for the first time.
3. Additions to existing products lines-new products that supplement established product lines (Package, Sizes, etc.)

4. Improvement and revisions of existing product - New products that Provide improved performance or greater perceived value and replace existing products.
5. Repositioning - Existing products that are targeted to new markets or market segments.
6. Cost Reduction - New products that provide similar performance at lower cost.

Stages of Product Evolution

When organizations, like financial institution in Nigeria, choose to go by the development of new products, they must establish some procedures for processing the ideas it uncovers. This procedure is called product evolution. Before a product is put on the market, it has to pass through seven (7) stages of evolution, and they are (1) idea generation, (2) idea screening (3) concept development and testing, (4) business analysis (5) beta testing and market testing (6) technical implementation and (7) commercialization.

1. Idea Generation: Ideas for new products can be obtained from customers (employing user innovation), the company's Research and Development department, competitors, focus groups, employees, sales people, corporate spies, trade shows, or through a policy of Open Innovation. Ethnographic discovery methods (searching for user patterns and habits) may also be used to get an insight into new product lines or product features. Formal idea generation techniques can be used, such as attribute listing, forced relationships, brainstorming, morphological analysis and problem analysis.

2. Idea Screening: The object is to eliminate unsound concepts prior to devoting resources to them. The screeners must ask at least three questions: (1) Will the customers in the target market benefit from the product? (2) Is it technically feasible to manufacture the product e.g. ATM Cards. Will the product be profitable when manufactured and delivered to the customers at the target price?

3. Concept Development and Testing: This involves developing and marketing and engineering which include (1) Who is the target market and who is the decision maker in the purchasing process? (2) What product features must the product incorporate? (3) What benefits will the product provide? (4) How will consumers react to the product? (5) How will the product be produced most cost effectively? (6) Can it prove feasible through virtual computer aided rendering, and rapid prototyping? (7) What will it cost to produce the product? (8) Test the concept by asking a sample of prospective customers what they think of the idea.

4. Business Analysis: The business analysis aspect in the stages of the product includes (1) Estimating the likely selling price based upon competition and customer feedback (2) Estimating sales volume based upon size of the market (3) Estimating profitability and breakeven point. 5.

5. Beta and Market Testing: This stage involves (1) Producing a physical prototype or mock-up of the product (2) Testing the product (and its packaging) in typical usage situations (3) Conducting focus group customer interviews or introduce at trade show (4) Make adjustments where necessary (5) Produce an initial run of the product and sell it in a test market area to determine customer acceptance.

6. Technical implementation: This aspect of the process includes the followings: (1) New programme initiation (2) Resource estimation (3) Requirement publication (4) Engineering operations planning (5) Department scheduling (6) Supplier collaboration (7) Logistics plan (8) Resources plan publication (9) Programme review and monitoring (10) Contingencies and what-if planning.

7. Commercialization: This is often considered as post-new- product development, and the process include: (1) Launching the product (2) Producing and placing advertisements and other promotions (3) Filling the distribution pipeline with the product (4) Critical Path Analysis is most useful at this stage.

Product Life Cycle and Its Implications to Product Development Product lifecycle influences relate to a particular stage in the services existence - either, it is the introduction, growth, maturity or decline stage. Recognizing the various stages is important and can influence the ways in which marketing mix is applied. Many products and services come and go over a period of time. It is helpful to the marketing manager to know the points in the product lifecycle reached by an existing product, the likely time span of proposed new product as well as the type of product lifecycle, which applies to his product. The stages are:

A. Product Development Stage:

This is when there are only out flows since money is invested in design cost, the product launch takes place.

B. The introduction Stage:

This stage is characterized by slow growth in sales and services and possibly negative profit. Expenses incurred from the services at this early stage are high, as efforts are made to gain wide spread acceptance quickly. This stage includes market research, cost, expenditure in establishing the distribution systems, test marketing e.t.c. The main activity at this stage is to intensify efforts in promoting the product or services.

C. The Growth Stage:

During this stage, an increase in volume occurs while costs tend to remain stable. Sales are increasing at a gradual rate. Profitability will increase as economies of scale come into play.

D. The Maturity Stage:

This occurs when overcapacity which occurs at the profitability of the growth stage encourages competitors to enter the scene. There will be dropping of sales, increased advertising, increasing costs and declining profit margins.

E. The Saturation Stage:

This is characterized by stable fixed costs but reducing revenue especially if price have been cut. At this stage, the bank could terminate or withdraw the service completely and thereby arrest any losses that may be arising.

THE ROLE OF THE MARKETING MIX PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

Marketing mix can be said to be packaged for satisfaction provided by the marketing function to the consumer. It represents what variables the marketer must combine in order to influence the largest number of consumers. It can be defined as a combination of pricing policies and practices and the method used in promotion. They are traditionally referred to as practices and the method used in promotion. They are traditionally referred to as the 4P'S of marketing, The basis of the designing of the marketing mix to the determination of why people buy. Some of the reasons why people buy are:; psychology of ownership; people want to own properties and goods especially where a social prestige is attached. People also buy because they make a good purchase etc. A good marketer must incorporate all these into the design of his marketing mix so as to be able to influence demand for his product.

A. Product

This is the offering of the company to the market, It is what the customers consume to satisfy their needs. Issues relating to the product in the marketing mix transcend the physical appearance of the product and touch more of its attributes, most of which at times are not designable by physical inspection. Some attributes include the quality of the product, the convenience and perfection in packaging. Other issues include the branding of the product and the positioning of the product in the mind of the customers in terms of the various features possessed by the product.

B. Price

Price is the fore going made by a buyer to consume his benefit derivable from a product. Price can be determined by the market forces in the situation of perfect product. Perfect competition; otherwise the company

sets it after taking a lot of factors (like the cause of manufacture, competitive pressures, legal factors, distributive cause and other similar factors) into consideration. In order to attract patronage, the price change by the company for its offering must be reasonable, profitable and competitive.

C. Promotion

This includes all methods used in providing information to the consumer about the product in a bid to induce him to buy. Promotion has its own mix in terms of its components, which must be carefully combined in various proportions to get the best result. It includes advertising, personnel selling, sales promotion and public relations. In recent times, marketing experts have added other components which include direct marketing, packaging and sponsorship.

D. Place

This includes the process and procedure, physical and otherwise of making the goods available at the right place and at the right time. Consideration in this regard includes the channels of distribution solution i.e. The most effective channel should be used.

E. People

The process adopted by a company in carrying out its operations is a major determinant of its success and therefore forms part of its marketing mix. Process and procedures may be time-consuming and wasteful.³²

The Structure of the Nigerian Financial System

The Nigerian Financial System can be broadly subdivided into two (2), namely: the informal and the formal. The informal sector comprises the local money lenders, the thrifts and savings associations etc. This component is poorly developed, limited in reach, and not integrated into the formal financial system. Financial system on the other hand, can be subdivided into capital and money market institutions and non bank financial institutions. The institutions are regulated by the Federal Ministry of Finance (FMF), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Nigeria Deposit

Insurance Corporation (NDIC), Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), National Insurance Commission (NIACOM), Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN), and the National Board for community Banks. This Nigerian financial service industry comprises banking, capital markets, insurance asset management, pensions and other financial sector. The breakdown of this composition follows in the chart below and the structure of the industry is represented in the figure

SECTORS OPERATIONS AND REGULATION

There are six sectors in Nigeria's financial service industry; banking insurance, capital market, pensions, asset management, and other financial institutions.

Banking

- Deposit Money Banks (DMBS) are the dominant operations in the industry, being the biggest in size and profitability. There are currently 25 deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- Micro Finance Banks are financial institution licensed to provide credit, banking and other financial services to a designated catchment area or community.

There are 757 community banks in Nigeria. In December 2005, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) issued new regulations mandating community banks to convert to Micro Banks (MFBs) by December 2007. This will require the community banks to increase their minimum paid-up capital significantly from N5 million to N20 million for those converting to unit MFBS or N1 billion for those converting to state, MFBs.

- Primary Mortgage Institution (PMIs), also called Saving and Loans company, are specialized institution which collect household O savings and originate mortgage loans. PMIs fund the loans from brudeposits and hold the loans on their books until maturity. There are about ninety (90) primary mortgage institutions of Nigeria.
- Trustee and Trust Companies are typically subsidiaries of banks. They provide fund management services for organizations or individual who set up trust funds. Their services also include portfolio management, investment advisory, property management and custodial services for non-pension assets.
- Insurance Insurance Companies: The insurance sector is the second largest sector in the financial services industry, comprising over a hundred insurance companies. The minimum capital requirement is N3 billion for companies that provide non-life insurance.
- Re-insurance Companies: There are currently five re-insurance companies in Nigeria. In September 2005, the Federal Ministry of Finance and the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) increased the minimum capital base for a re-insurance business in Nigeria to N10 billion starting from February 2007.
- Insurance Brokers: There are about 510 brokers registered with the NAICOM, of which only a few control a significant proportion (80%) of risks and hence, premium income of the industry.
- Loss adjusters advise insurance companies on valuation. There are about 40 loss adjusters in Nigeria.

- Insurance Agents are representative of Insurers employed either on part-time or full-time to market insurance policies on commission. There are over 5,000 registered insurance agents in Nigeria.

Capital Markets

- Issuing House provide traditional investment banking services, acting as intermediaries in capital market activities. They operate between the company whose shares are being sold, the regulatory authorities and the public. Issuing houses, which are registered with and regulated by the Securities and Exchange commission structure the entire transaction, sponsor and represent issuing company. Issuing Company. Most of issuing houses in Nigeria are affiliates of deposit money banks.
- Stock brokers are involved in the business of trading capital market securities. There are currently about 581 licensed stock brokers.

Pension

The pension fund market in Nigeria is worth an estimated N3000 billion (US \$2.5 billion) and has an estimated annual growth rate of 15%.

- Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) manage pension assets and administer retirement benefits under the new pension regime. There are currently 13 PFAs licensed in Nigeria. The National Pension Commission (PENCOM) Regulates the PFAs.
- Pension Funds Custodians (PFCs) hold the pension assets on behalf of contributors and settle transactions arising from pension fund management. There are currently 4 licensed PFCs in Nigeria. Oral shop M operatio

Assets Management

- Private equity and mutual funds are in the infant stages in Nigeria. There are just a handful of private fund managers in the country and most of the private equity firms are offshoots of foreign firms. Notwithstanding, there is growing interest in Nigeria from international private equity investors.

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Other Financial Institutions

- Discount houses specialize in trading money securities, with a specific mandate to provide liquidity and play market-making roles for terms money market instruments.. There are five (5) discount houses in Nigeria.
- Finance companies are financial institutions whose business and primary functions include lending to individuals. Finance companies do not accept deposits. There are 112 Finance companies in Nigeria. There are also about 126 licensed Bureau de change in Nigeria.
- Development Finance Institution (DFIs) is usually a government owned financial institution established to finance certain development objectives of the government objectives mainly in the agriculture, commerce, and industrial There are six (6) DFIs in Nigeria. sectors of the economy.

Financial Institutions Regulatory Agencies

The Federal Ministry of Finance (FMF) advises the Federal government on its fiscal operations and cooperates with CBN on monetary matters. It is at the top of the financial system, and until recently, the CBN was under its control. However, the recent amendment to the laws of the CBN compels the CBN to report to the Presidency through the Federal Ministry of Finance.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN): This is the apex authority in the financial system. Among its primary functions, the Bank promotes monetary stability and a sound financial system, and acts as banker and financial adviser to the federal government, as well as flexibility in regulating and overseeing the banking sector and licensing finance companies which hitherto operated outside any regulatory framework. The Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC): Although an autonomous entity from the CBN, it complements the regulatory and supervisory role of the CBN.

NDIC commenced operations in 1989 with the aim of providing deposit insurance and related service for banks in order to promote confidence in the banking industry. It examines the books of Deposit Money Banks and Financial Institutions.

The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC): Formerly known as the Capital Issues Commission, secretary is the apex regulatory authority of the capital market. Its objective is to promote an orderly an active capital market by ensuring the adequate protection of securities, registering all securities dealers in order to maintain proper standards of conduct and professionalism, approving and regulating mergers and acquisitions and maintaining surveillance over the market to enhance efficiency.

National Insurance Commission (NAICOM): The NAICOM is charged with effective administration, supervision, regulation, and control of the business of insurance in Nigeria. It ensures adequate capitalization and reserve, good management, high technical expertise and judicious fund placement in the insurance industry.

The Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN): This is the successor of the Nigerian Building Society. It provides banking and advisory services, and undertakes research activities pertaining to housing. With the adoption of the National Housing Policy in 1990, FMBN was empowered to regulate primary mortgage institutions in Nigeria. The financing function of FMBN was carved out and transferred to the Federal Mortgage Finance, while the FMBN retained the regulatory role. FMBN is under the control of the CBN.

Financial Services Coordinating Committee (FSCC): This is a committee established to coordinate the activities of all regulatory institutions in the financial system. The Committee is chaired by the Federal Minister of Finance.

The Money Market

The money market segment of the financial system constitutes the hub of the financial system. Its major function is to facilitate the raising of short- term funds from the surplus sectors to the deficit sectors of the economy and comprises the discount houses, commercial and merchant banks, the special purpose banks like the Community Banks and the defunct Peoples Bank of Nigeria.

The Discount Houses

These are non-bank financial institutions that mobilize funds for investment in securities according to the liquidity needs of the system. Discount house were created to serve as financial intermediaries between the CBN, licensed banks and other financial institutions. Five discount houses are currently in operation in Nigeria.

Commercial and Merchant Bank

The institutions operate under the legal framework of the Banks and other Financial Institutions Act 25 of 1991 (as amended). The commercial banks. The bank was expected to facilitate access to credit of the urban poor scale operators and thereby Increase their self-reliance. As of 1996, the bank had 275 branches and total assets of N 1.073 billion.

The Community Banks

A Community Bank in Nigeria is a self-sustaining financial institution owned and managed within a community to provide financial services to that community. The National Board for Community Banks (NBCB) has issued provisional licenses to 1,366 Community Banks. Final license is issued by the CBN after operating for two years.

Development finance Institutions (DFIs)

Specialized banks or Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) have been established to contribute to the development of specific sectors of the economy. They consist of the Nigeria Industrial Developmental Bank (NIDB), Nigeria Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank (NACB), and Urban Development Bank. Like other financial institutions, all development banks are now under the supervision of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN).

The Capital Market

The Nigerian Capital Market is a channel for mobilizing long-term funds. The main institution is the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), which is at the apex and serves as the regulatory authority of the market, the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), the issuing houses and the stock broking firms. The capital market is classified into primary and secondary segments. The Nigeria Stock Exchange commenced into primary and secondary segments. The Nigeria Stock Exchange commenced business in 1961. To encourage small as well as large-scale enterprises gain access to public listing, the NSE operates the main exchange for relatively large enterprises and the Second-Securities Market (SSM), where listing requirements are less stringent, for small and medium scale enterprises.

The Primary Market: This is a market for new issues of securities. The mode of offer for the securities traded in this market includes offer for subscription, right issues, offer for sale and private placements.

The Secondary Market: This is a market for trading in existing securities.

This consists of exchange and over-the-counter markets where securities are bought and sold after their issuance in the primary market. Activities in the secondary market have increased substantially over the years. There are six trading floors in Nigeria namely: Lagos, Kaduna, Port-Harcourt, Ibadan, Kano and Onitsha.

The Unit Trust Scheme

This is a mechanism for mobilizing the financial resources of small and big savers and managing such funds to achieve maximum returns with minimum risks through efficient portfolio diversification. Unit Trusts have functioned since 1990 and there are now 14.

Recent Developments in the Nigerian Financial System

A new insurance was also promulgated which stipulates new capital requirements for insurance companies and also created the National Insurance Commission as the regulatory organ in the industry.

A computerized trading system was introduced in the Nigeria Stock Exchange and enhance processing and settlement of transactions and facilitates the internationalization of the Exchange.

The Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation Decree 22 of 1988 was amended to give more powers to the Corporation to deal with insured banks and to act independent of the CBN on some matters affecting problem banks.

With specific reference to the banking system, it is necessary to comment on the antecedents to the reforms in this sector. As at the end of June 2004, there were 89 banks with many banks having capital base of less than USD 10 million, and about 3,300 branches. Structurally, the sector is highly concentrated as the ten largest banks account for about 20 per cent of the industry's total assets/liabilities. Even the largest bank in Nigeria has a capital base of about US\$24 million compared to US\$26 million for the smallest bank in Malaysia. The small size of the banks, each with expensive headquarters, separate investment in software and hardware, heavy fixed costs and operating expenses, and with bunching of branches in the commercial centres resulted in very high average cost for the industry. This in turn has implications for the cost of intermediation, the spread between deposit and lending rate, and puts undue pressure on banks to engage in sharp practices as means of survival. Most of the banks were not engaged in strict savings intermediation, but were merely traders. To many of such banks, depositors with balances of less than N50,000 to N100,000 are not welcome. The implication was toward high net-worth agents for deposits from government agencies, bluechip companies and rich individuals. Without prejudice to the existence of a huge informal economy, the alienation of small depositors could be blamed for the existence of over N400 billion outside the banking system as at 2004. Also real sector operations in agriculture /SME and manufacturing suffered neglect. This situation is neither sustainable nor healthy for the economy.

As at the end of March 2004, the CBN's ratings of all banks classified 62 as sound/satisfactory. 14 as marginal and 11 as unsound, while 2 of the

banks did not render returns during the period. The fundamental problems of the banks, particularly those classified unsound have been identified to include: persistent illiquidity, poor assets quality and unprofitable operations. Generally, the major problems of many Nigerian banks include:

- Weak corporate governance, evidenced by high turnover in the board and management staff, inaccurate reporting and non-compliance with regulatory requirements, falling ethics and unhealthy competition.
- Late or non-publication of annual accounts that obviates the impact of market discipline in ensuring banking soundness.
- Gross insider abuses, resulting in huge non-performing insider related credits
- Insolvency, as evidenced by negative capital adequacy ratios and shareholder's funds that had been completely eroded by operating losses.
- Weak capital base, even for those banks that have met the minimum capital requirement of N1 billion as at 2004.
- Over-dependency on public sector deposits, and neglect of small and medium class savers.

Elements of the Reforms (The Reform Agenda)

The recent reforms in the Nigeria Financial System is essentially as a subset of the overall economic reform agenda of the government branded as "The National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS). The initiative aims to transform Nigeria through a comprehensive plan that focuses on:

- Value reorientation
- Wealth creation
- Employment generation
- Poverty reduction

To achieve these goals, NEED proposes a framework that encompasses empowering people, promoting private enterprise and changing the way government does its work. The strategies of NEEDS include:

- Privatize, deregulate and liberalize the key sectors
- Co-ordinate sectoral development strategies for agriculture, industry (especially SMEs) and services (especially tourism)
- Develop infrastructure, especially electricity, transport and water.
- Stimulate real sector financing by mobilizing cheap long-term all savings
- Create effective regulatory regimes.
- Execute programmes targeted at private sector growth. Some of the goals of NEEDS are
- GDP growth rates of 5% 2004, 6% in 2006, and 7% in 2007
- A 5% reduction in the incidence of poverty every year from 2003 to 2007
- Achieve reduced inflation from 2005 and sustain it thereafter.
- Earn US\$3 billion in agricultural exports by 2007
- Achieving 70% manufacturing capacity utilization
- Increasing power generation from 6000mw to 10,000mw.

The overall agenda for the reforms as it affects the financial system, and as summarized by the Governor of the Central Bank, include the following main elements:

- Ensuring exchange rate and price stability
- Managing interest rate for stability and development
- Macroeconomic coordination
- Vigorous pursuit of the developmental role of the Central Bank Improvement of the payment system
- Financial sector diversification and regulatory reforms
- Strategies for integrating Nigeria's financial system into the African regional and global financial system.

The first phase of the economic reforms designed to ensure a diversified, strong reliable banking sector is strengthening and consolidating the banking system. This is expected to ensure the safety of depositors money: Play active development roles in the Nigerian economy, and make Nigerian Banks competent and competitive players in the African regional and global financial system. The overall beneficiaries of the reforms would be the ordinary depositors who will have the assurance of their funds

safety, the entrepreneur at all levels, who will have a stronger financial system to finance their businesses, and the Nigerian economy which will benefit from internationally connected and competitive banks working to mobilize international capital for the development of Nigeria.

The second phase of the reforms addresses the issues of diversification, including programmes to encourage the emergence of regional and unit/ specialized banks.

Emerging Responsibilities for the Financial Services Sector

The successful executive of the NEEDS initiative creates enormous responsibilities for the financial system. Some of the responsibilities of the financial services sector are:

- Provision of long-term financing for big projects, especially financing of infrastructure, with emphasis on power, transport and water.
- Efficient financing of importation
- Financing the development of local content in the oil exploration and production, and other extractive industries.
- Financing agriculture to achieve the target growth rate of 6% p.a, and achieve a food exports target of USD\$3 billion by 2007.
- Financing of the construction of affordable houses, and providing mortgage of appropriate tenors at affordable interest rates to citizen.
- Provision of start-up and working capital for SMEs Provision of venture capital for commercialization of technological innovations.
- Provision of micro-credits to strengthen the informal sector, increase productivity and reduce poverty.
- Provision of financing for the above activities as cheaply as possible, with interest rate not exceeding the early teens, but preferably within the single digit band.
- Simultaneously with low interest rates, NEEDS requires capacity for substantial medium and long term financing.

These far reaching demands on the financial services sector have been further crystalized into tangible, specific measurable projects as follows:

- Power generation infrastructure costs US\$1m per mega watt (N798 billion)
- Rail rehabilitation - 50% of the US\$ 60 billion as estimated by the Federal Ministry of Transport (N3.000bn)
- Investment of US\$ 1 billion required to generate US\$3 billion agricultural export (N 133bn)
- 250,000 affordable houses to cost N5 Million per house (N1.187bn)
- Creation of 250,000 SME jobs at an investment of N250,000 per job (N63bn)
- Venture capital for commercializing inventions US\$250 million (N33bn)
- Micro-credits at N10,000 for 500,000 borrowers (N5bn)
- Local content in crude oil exploration production, and refining (N1,33bn)

Emerging Challenges of Economic and Financial System reforms

The financing requirement of NEEDS from 2003-2007 has thus been put at N7.5 trillion (US\$57.1bn). The desired financing has to be of medium and long term nature, with low interest rates, ideally single digit. Incidentally, the total asset base of the entire Nigerian banking industry is estimated at a mere US\$24 billion, while the deposit base is a paltry US\$15 billion. Lending rates are in the region of late teens and beyond, and lending is concentrated in the short-term owing to the death of long- term savings. The quantum of government domestic debt by way of Treasury bills and bills alone (about 72%) relative of domestic deposits constitutes a major impediment to project financing.

Meanwhile, the financial strength of other financial services providers in the system is equally small as shown below:

- Meanwhile, the financial strength of other financial services of US\$17bn as at June 2004.

- Insurance total assets of US\$7bn, and market gross premium of N37bn.
- Primary mortgage institution: Total asset base (US\$500m), and capital of US\$20m in 2003.
- Development finance institutions permanent capital of US\$48m.

The huge gap between financing needs and the available financing capacity, represents major growth opportunities in project financing, and accords with one NEEDS strategy of stimulating real sector financing by mobilizing cheap long-term savings. It can not be over-emphasized that the NEEDS can not be successfully financed without a complete reform of the financial system.

In order to improve the capacity services industry to meet the financing requirements of NEEDS, five reform imperatives have been proposed thus:

- Reduction of Government demand for credit to induce interest rate reduction and increase the quantum of credit available to the private sector.
- Non-inflationary increase in the supply of deposits to induce interest rate reduction.
- Reform of the Dutch Auction system to lower the cost of financing mobilize cheap long-term savings, thus improving the capital of banks and financial institutions in specialized sectors.
- Eliminate inefficiencies and wastes in the management of Public Sector Interventions in Specialized Sectors. The model of using specialized development institutions to meet the needs of the real sector which financial institutions relying purely on market forces would avoid, appears to have achieved limited success globally. and is even worse in our local case. This is the case with numerous government institutions and parastatals most of which have other lapping functions and are bugged down by bureaucracy. Just like the Pension reforms, the National Housing Fund could be reformed by strengthening the capital base of Mortgage Banks. and allow contributors to choose the Mortgage Banks for the domiciliation of their contributions.

- Also tax, credit and similar fiscal measures could be given to commercial banks as an incentive for mortgage finance, project and development lending. Also the strengthening of the equity base of the insurance institutions has been carried out to enhance their underwriting and risk retention capacity.

With specific references to the banking sector, the diversification of the productive base of the economy remains a fundamental challenge of economic management, and banks will increasingly be challenged to become more innovative in their intermediation functions and especially to increase financing to the productive sector. Some of the key elements of the reform that will position banks to rise up to these challenges include:

- Minimum capitalization requirement of N25 billion
- Consolidation of banking institutions through mergers and acquisitions.
- Adoption of risk focused, and rule-based regulatory framework
- Closer collaboration with the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) in the establishment of Financial intelligence and enforcement of the anti-money laundering and other economic crime measures.
- Developing new products Building new branches
- Increasing market share and profitability number of shareholders.

The Reform and Prospects in the Financial Sector

As at the end of December 2005, the financial system comprised of CBN, the Nigeria deposit insurance corporation (NDIC), the securities and Exchange Commission, Community Banks, 112 finance companies, 126 bureau-de-change, 1 stock exchange, 1 commodity exchange, 5 discount houses, 90 primary mortgage institutions, 6 development institutions, 103 insurance companies, and 581 stock brokers.

1. The Recapitalization and Consolidation of the Banking Sector:

For the banking sector, recapitalization and consolidation have been

completed with the emergence of 25 Banks from 89 universal banks pre- consolidation. The 25 Banks have an aggregate shareholders fund of N811 billion, a 177.74% growth relative to preconsolidation position. The African Economy survey also shows that the consolidation was so successful that the banking system became awash with funds, much of it coming from the capital market.

Also in keeping with the central banks' determination to stabilize prices and curtail inflation through monetary policy instruments, an ambience of civility in lending interest rates is gradually emerging.

Key prospects that have emerged from the reforms that will directly or indirectly impact interest on the rural sector include:

1. The opportunity to create mortgage loans and a market to mortgage backed securities. Estimated market potential is in excess of N18 trillion (US\$136BN)
2. Creating a market for consumer finance and micro-credit. The huge population of the country and the growing new middle class present a very viable opportunity to develop this market.
3. Developing the concept of Bancassurance in the country.
4. Creating and developing a market in long-tem debt instruments. This includes government bonds, corporate bonds, and Asset- backed securities.
5. Syndication of large ticket deals in the turn key agro-allied projects, oil and gas telecom, infrastructure and energy sectors.
6. Corporate and project Finance opportunities
7. Venture capital business
8. Pursuance of the NEEDS requirement of achieving 6% growth for the agricultural sector.

2. The Pension Reforms:

The 2004 Pensions Reform Act established a uniform, contributory; private sector managed and fully funded pension system for both the public and the private sectors of the country. The expected outcomes include:

- Pension Fund Administration: Compulsory savings would mobilize long-term funds in the country. The size of the pension funds markets is estimated at N300bn (\$25bn) with a projected growth rate of about 15% p.a.
- Corporate Finance and Financial Advisory: Creation and development of market for long-term securities such as bonds, mortgages and other asset management and custodianship.

3. The Capital Market Reforms:

- The reforms taking place in the banking and pensions sectors are affecting this sector and portend new opportunities here.
- Over \$1bn has been raised in the market by banks who are seeking to recapitalize, lending to a deepening of the market.
- The pension reforms would create a pool of long-term funds which would be channeled into the market to further deepen it.
- More companies are beginning to see the benefits and are going to this market to raise funds.
- Increasing activities in primary market with huge potential for increased activities in the secondary market.
- Development of Commodity Exchange to deal in agro-allied commodities.

Development Finance Institutions: The Bank of Industries has been recapitalized to play more effective role in project finance. Also, the Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative Bank was merged with Peoples Bank and the Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) to form the Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB). This ensures minimization of wastes, and a focused intervention in agricultural and rural finance.

Furthermore, the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS) of the Central Bank has also been rejuvenated with added incentives as the interest Draw Back Scheme. Reflecting the need to develop the small and medium enterprises, the Government established the small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) as a vehicle for government support to SME. This has been complemented by the small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS). The scheme is purely a private initiative of the Bankers Committee designed to support SMEs which are acclaimed as engines of economic growth.

Towards meeting the projected growth rate for the agricultural sector and diversifying the economy, the Federal Government spearheaded the creation of the Agricultural Credit Support Scheme. The aim is to raise N50 billion from the private and public sector for investment in agricultural production in the 2006 farming season alone. This initiative is fully on course.

In all, the financial system reforms would affect the size, structure and tenor of deposits available to financial institutions. It is expected that longer tenure and low priced funds would be at the disposal of these institutions for intermediation purpose. The increased availability of funds of the right kind will go a long way to enhance the agriculture, SME and rural outreach of the financial sector.

5. Insurance Institutions:

- Reduced from 168 to 71 insurance and reinsurance companies (43 general; 26 life and 2 Re-insurance) with no company liquidating: only mergers and acquisitions were encouraged.

- Recapitalization from N1- 10b depending on the nature of Business.

Let's now briefly look at the issue of prospects and challenges of product development in the post-consolidation era before we conclude this paper.

Prospects of New Product Development in the Financial Industry include:

- Significant improvement in service delivery
- Lending to real sector including agriculture, manufacturing and so on
- Deploying of ICT to develop new products.
- Fewer banks in the market (from 89 to 25 banks); also fewer insurance companies.
- Opportunity to increase market share
- Large population base (over 140 million Nigerians)

Prospects of Product Development in the Post-Consolidation Financial Industry

The financial industry is awash with cash after the consolidation exercise. Stake shareholders who have invested in the industry expect returns on their investment. This has forced the industry to think of innovative products and services.

Some of the successful innovative products that have come after the consolidation exercise include:

- Fee Automated Teller Machines (ATM Cards)
- On-line banking
- Telephone banking
- Commission-on Transaction (COT) free banking
- Account opening without deposit (operated by UBA and some other banking institutions)
- Mobile banking (Bank on wheels operated by GT Bank)
- Current account with interest
- Product account with interest.
- Statements for kids such as kids saving accounts Statement by e-mail
- Flexible insurance

- Leasing
- Home ownership schemes.
- Assets purchase scheme.

Challenges and Failure of New Product Development in the Financial Industry

Given today's intense competition in the financial industry, companies that fail to develop new products are putting themselves at great risk. Their existing products are vulnerable to changing consumer needs and tastes new technologies, shortened product life cycles, and increased competition. At the same time, new-product development is risky. New products continue to fail at disturbing rate. The new product failure rate of packaged goods (consisting mostly of line extensions) is estimated at 80%. Clancy and Shulman believe that the same high failure rate befalls new financial products and services, such as credit cards, insurance plans, and brokerage services (Kotler - 1999).

Factors responsible for new products failure include:

- A high-level executive might push a favourite idea through in spite of negative market research finding.
- The idea is good, but the market size is over estimated.
- The actual product is not well designed
- The new product is incorrectly positioned in the market, not advertised effectively or over-priced.
- Development costs are higher than expected Competitors fights back harder than expected
- Shortages of important new-product ideas.
- Fragmented markets.
- Social and governmental constraints. CBN might come up with conditions about corporate governance or ethical practices.
- Religious reasons (Islamic non interest banking)
- Faster development time Shorter life cycle.
- Shorted life cycle.

Conclusion

The Post-Consolidation era for the financial industry opens up av opportunities for new product development. Even as these opportunes exist, organizations wanting to bring to the market place new products should try to overcome the challenges and pitfalls highlighted in the new product development stages so as to enhance success. To be competitive, business needs a predictable legal environment Law should be used as a vehicle to fast-track the development of Nigeria's Financial Services Systems to be the safest and fastest growing among emerging markets. To accomplish the goal of making the legal framework for Nigeria's Financial Services the most robust, globally competitive and market friendly, there is the need to reform the Judicial sector for speed, efficient and transparent dispute resolution: harmonize conflicting legislation and regulations in Financial Service Sector for the international financial centre. nstalments

In addition, existing promulgated new laws should be amended to enhance efficiency in the legal system.

Finally, in spite of the challenges highlighted, it is crystal clear that the financial institutions in Nigeria has taken a quantum leap in the right direction and would in no time be able to compete effectively in the global financial market. However, in order to fully achieve the desired level, the key challenges earlier mentioned must be adequately addressed.

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